

UNLOCKING CULTURAL EXCHANGE: FUNCTIONALISM IN STANDARDIZING RED TOURISM ENGLISH TRANSLATION

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Abstract

China's rapidly growing tourism industry, driven by its expanding engagement with the world, is increasingly making use of English materials to facilitate tourist access to its remarkable "Red tourism" resources. Red tourism, as a novel form of tourism, embodies unique allure and profound cultural significance. Hence, it is paramount to address the existing challenges in the English translation of Red tourism materials.

Functional theory, a contemporary approach to text translation, underscores the purposive and systematic nature of translation. In recent years, functionalism has been successfully applied across diverse domains in China. As a pivotal facet of cultural exchange, English translation in Red tourism aims to introduce China's rich "Red culture" to international tourists. In line with functionalist principles, this paper underscores the need for text and reader analysis when confronting translation issues, placing the translator at the heart of the translation process.

Considering the paramount importance of English translation for Red tourism in China, this paper advocates standardized strategies to enhance the quality and proficiency of Red tourism translation efforts.

1. Introduction

With the deepening of China's opening to the outside world, the tourism industry is developing vigorously. In this process, a large number of English materials provide convenient conditions for tourists to understand red tourism resources, and also lay a foundation for them to smoothly visit scenic spots [1]. As a new tourism activity, Red tourism has its unique charm and connotation [2-3]. Therefore, it is of great significance to study the existing problems in English translation of red tourism [4]. Functional theory is a new theory centered on text translation, which emphasizes that translation is purposeful and systematic [5]. In recent years, functionalism has been widely

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applied and achieved good results in various fields in China. As an important form of cultural communication, the purpose of Red tourism English translation is to promote China's excellent red culture to foreign tourists, so this should be taken into account when translating Red tourism English. Functionalism emphasizes text analysis and reader analysis when solving translation problems, and points out that the translator should be at the center of the translation process. Therefore, from the perspective of functionalism, based on the importance of English translation of Red tourism in China at present, this paper proposes corresponding standardization strategies in order to promote the quality and level of Red tourism translation.

2. Connotation of red tourism

With the promotion of the popularity of Chinese culture, Red tourism, as a part of Chinese tourism and cultural activities, has become the preferred tourism activity for foreign tourists to understand Chinese red stories. It is not only responsible for spreading Chinese revolutionary history and culture, revolutionary deeds, but also promoting Chinese revolutionary spirit. Therefore, Red tourism translation, as a form of interpreting Red tourism culture, came into being[6]. The translation of Red tourism takes language as the form carrier, foreign tourists as the leading object, and uses another language form to help them better understand the Chinese revolutionary culture.

At present, China's red tourism is mainly divided into four categories: patriotic education type, revolutionary traditional education type, military training type and ecological recreation type. As an important tourism resource in our country, red tourism has the following characteristics:

- (1) Epochal. The development of red tourism is closely related to the background of The Times, and it is an important way to educate patriotism and revolutionary tradition.
- (2) Regionalism. Since red tourism mainly involves the revolutionary ruins in various regions of our country, each region should excavate and organize them according to its own characteristics.
- (3) Educational. The function of red tourism education is prominent, emphasizing education in both content and form.
- (4) Economy. As red tourism resources are highly attractive and can bring economic benefits to tourists, local governments and travel agencies are more inclined to develop and operate red tourism projects.

3. The Importance of Red tourism Translation

At present, there are more than 400 Red tourism scenic spots in China. Although the distribution of Red tourism scenic spots is relatively scattered, and the proportion of tourism in China's economic construction is relatively small, this has not hindered the growth of the number of tourists. However, due to cultural differences, Chinese tourists may have less understanding of local customs and culture before Red tourism, so they may not adapt to English translation[7]. From the perspective of functional theory, English translation of Red tourism in China has the following importance:

- (1) Avoiding the use of Chinglish can help foreign tourists understand scenic information. As the main information transmission medium of Red tourism scenic spots, English translation plays a vital role in the publicity of scenic spots. However, many tourist attractions use English translations that are different from traditional Chinese culture when promoting to the outside world, which makes it difficult for foreign tourists to understand the meaning behind them. For example, in the Memorial Hall of Jinggang Mountains Revolutionary base area, there is a classic slogan "Jinggang Mountains is the cradle of Chinese revolution", but the word "cradle" does not exist in English, and there is no similar expression in Chinese. Although this is only a minor issue, it may hinder foreign tourists' understanding of revolutionary holy sites.

(2) The matching between the target language and the source language helps to improve the understanding of the source language information. Language is the carrier of culture, and different countries have different cultural backgrounds[8]. People express their thoughts and emotions through language. Therefore, these cultural differences need to be taken into account in the English translation of Red tourism. However, in many English translations of Red tourism attractions, due to the influence of cultural differences, it is difficult for tourists to understand the content expressed. To address this issue, more consideration needs to be given to cultural differences in the translation process to ensure that tourists can accurately understand the source language information.

4. Translation theory from the perspective of functionalism

Functional theory is a translation theory that arose in Germany in the 1960s and was put forward by the German linguists Reiss and Vermeer. This theory holds that translation should be purpose-oriented rather than textual. Functional theory divides texts into two categories: one is purely functional, such as propaganda texts; The other is purposeful, such as advertising, promotional materials, cultural materials and so on. Translation is to transform the linguistic form of the source text into the linguistic form of the target text according to functionalism[9]. As a new translation theory, functionalism plays an important role in solving many problems in the field of translation. On the one hand, it can effectively guide translators to follow translation strategies and principles during the translation process, thereby ensuring the functional realization of the translation; On the other hand, it also plays a positive role in guiding the translation of Red tourism English. In specific practice, the translator needs to understand the Red tourism English materials thoroughly to ensure the consistency between the translation and the original. At the same time, for some professional vocabulary that cannot be accurately grasped, conduct in-depth analysis and exploration to ensure that the translation is clear and easy to understand; Fully understand and utilize functional theory, and correctly use various translation techniques and strategies.

Functionalists believe that the translation process should be a "purpose" guided process. The so-called "purpose" is the effect and purpose to be achieved by translation. The so-called "behavior" means that the translation must conform to the functional requirements of the whole translation. If there is no goal, but only the "means" are satisfied, the translation will only backfire. In addition, translators must also pay attention to the social function of translation. From the perspective of social function, the expected effect of the translated text should be similar to that of the original text.

For the English translation of Red tourism, its purpose is to provide tourists with necessary information to help them better understand and appreciate the connotation of red culture. Therefore, when translating Red tourism English, the translator should focus on the main information and cultural background knowledge of the target language readers, and deal with its translation from the perspective of "function". To effectively convey the content and meaning of the original text, it is necessary to ensure that the translation retains the stylistic features and information of the original text to the greatest extent possible, and highlights its characteristics.

5. Research on standardization strategies for English translation of red tourism

The implementation of the standardization strategy must be based on the establishment of a systematic standard for Red tourism English translation. The effective implementation of the standardization strategy of Red tourism English translation from the perspective of functionalism will help improve the quality of Red tourism English translation and user experience, and further promote the development of Red tourism and enhance its international influence. Therefore, the following specification strategies are proposed in this paper:

(1) Establish a standard translation system for Red tourism attractions. This system should be the responsibility of a specialized agency that manages the translation of various scenic spots in a unified manner. At

the same time, establish a translation team composed of language experts, tourism experts, etc., responsible for providing comprehensive and systematic guidance to various scenic spots. At the same time, we should always follow the three basic principles in the process of Red tourism English translation. First, we should fully understand and grasp the specific situation of Red tourism attractions; Secondly, it is necessary to effectively handle languages from different cultural backgrounds; Finally, attention should be paid to the emotional experience of the translated readers. Make sure that the English translation of each scenic spot in the Red tourism Scenic Spot meets the needs of tourists from English speaking countries.

(2) Pay more attention to the construction of translation team. The lack of English language experts in China and the insufficient training of relevant talents lead to the low level of English translation for red tourism. Therefore, it is necessary to improve the level of Chinese red tourism English translation by strengthening the construction of talent team.

(3) Strengthen the monitoring and review of the translation quality of red tourist attractions. First of all, the quality of English translation in red tourist areas should be controlled. The quality of English translation in scenic spots directly affects the tourists' perception of scenic spots. Therefore, people with rich experience and professional knowledge should be responsible for the English translation of red tourist spots. Relevant departments should set up an effective review and supervision mechanism to strictly control the quality of English translation of red tourist attractions. For example, establish a standard system for English translation of red tourism and formulate a unified standard; Regular assessment of translators is required.

(4) Strengthen publicity efforts for foreign tourists in scenic spots. Scenic spots are different from general tourist attractions, and their audience includes not only domestic and foreign tourists, but also foreign scholars, experts, government officials, etc. Therefore, their translations should be easy for foreign tourists to understand and accept; In addition, it is necessary to strengthen the construction and promotion of the English official website or promotional materials for scenic spots, so that they can better exert their promotional effects.

6. Translation precautions

On the basis of implementing the above translation strategies, the following issues should also be considered in the process of standardization of Red tourism English translation from the perspective of functionalism:

(1) With the help of industry terms: Red tourism has some specific terms, for example, "Red tourism scenic spots" can be translated into "red tourism sites", with the help of these industry terms, relevant information can be accurately conveyed.

(2) Keep contextual coherence: When translating Red tourism content, pay attention to maintaining contextual coherence. Ensure that the content of the translation conforms to the background and theme of Red tourism, and can accurately convey relevant historical and cultural information.

(3) Pay attention to cultural differences: When translating the content of Red tourism, we should pay attention to the differences between Chinese and Western cultures. Some words and expressions may need to be properly adjusted so that English readers can better understand the connotation and background of Red tourism.

(4) Translation of publicity copy: for the publicity copy of Red tourism, attention should be paid to attracting readers' attention, brief introduction of relevant information, and highlighting its uniqueness and attraction.

(5) Pay attention to the target audience: when translating the content of Red tourism, you should consider who the final target audience is. Different audiences may have different understandings and needs of Red tourism, so it is necessary to choose appropriate expressions in translation.

(6) Cultural connotation understanding: In-depth understanding of the historical background, meaning and relevant details of Chinese red tourism culture. Only by mastering these cultural connotations can we accurately convey them to the target audience.

(7) Terminology accuracy: Use the correct terminology and professional vocabulary to describe red tourism-related content. Establish a unified English glossary of red tourism and follow the standardized use of terms.

(8) Context considerations: In the process of translation, contextual information should be considered to ensure that the meaning of the translation is complete, coherent and appropriate. Pay attention to factors such as context, tone, and language style.

7. Conclusion

Under the background of comprehensively promoting international cultural exchanges and cooperation in China, Red tourism has become an important part of the development of tourism industry. Therefore, we should vigorously develop the Red tourism industry, take this opportunity to constantly improve the quality of English translation of Red tourism, and constantly strengthen the spread of China's red culture to the outside world. To sum up, this paper discusses the problems and standardization strategies of Red tourism English translation from the perspective of functionalism, which can not only effectively improve the quality of Red tourism English translation, but also spread and promote China's Red tourism culture.

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